

Disruption of seasonal influenza circulation and evolution during the 2009 H1N1 and COVID-19 pandemics in Southeastern Asia

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This file contains all reviewer reports in order by version, followed by all author rebuttals in order by version.

Version 0:

Reviewer comments:

Reviewer #1

(Remarks to the Author)

Summary & Recommendation

This study offers insights into the spread of seasonal influenza A/H3N2 and B/Victoria globally and within Southeast Asia, a region known as a significant source of global influenza transmission. The author's examination of how the H1N1pdm09 and SARS-CoV-2 pandemics disrupted influenza transmission is a particularly relevant question. However, the study needs to improve in this regard.

Firstly, the comparison between the two pandemics is underdeveloped. Given each pandemic's distinct nature and impact, a more thorough comparison is warranted. The results tend to be overly descriptive, particularly in discussing travel disruptions, rather than delving into a deeper, more analytical comparison of the pandemics' effects on spread. For example, there are many instances where changes in air traffic are said to likely explain the differences. Though this is most certainly true, it is relatively shallow. Many of the claims could be tested, and more effort should be devoted to investigating the effect of the two pandemics in a statistically robust way besides simple descriptives.

Given this, many of the results echo findings from previous studies, which diminishes the originality of the work. Without additional investigation, many of the observations made and associated claims are presented circumstantially, with the remaining results mostly repeating previous work, which the authors indirectly acknowledge by frequently citing and noting the consistency of their findings with prior work.

The study would, therefore, benefit from a more robust statistical analysis quantifying the specific impacts of each pandemic on A/H3N2 and B/Victoria transmission. This would provide a better understanding of how these global events influenced seasonal influenza dynamics. I also felt there needed to be more about the ecological and public health implications of the results, with many important results presented without much interpretation.

As such, I recommend major revisions, including additional work, with more specific comments below.

Comments

1. The title should be more specific. which is specific to A/H3N2 and B/Victoria during the H1N1pdm09 and SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. e.g. Disruption of seasonal A/H3N2 and B/Victoria circulation ...". While it would be obvious why these two were chosen, it is better to be specific here and throughout, such as the subheadings.

2. Line 130. I think "Potential elimination" is a better term than disappearance.

3. Line 149: "First quarter of 2010" Please be specific about months(s) to avoid confusion.

4. Line 151 to 153: There are a number of claims throughout the paper, here included, that could be easily tested. Many results are presented descriptively alongside each other and hypothesised as causative but not tested. For example, it

should be simple enough to show the association between air traffic and the intensity of circulation controlling for seasonality. I've listed some additional areas where similar conclusions or loosely descriptive hypotheses are presented, which should be addressed with new work:

a. Line 187: "likely resulting in sustained exports from Southeastern Asia"

b. Line 209: "possibly due to the reduction of human mobility and subsequent lineage movement"

c. Line 264 "The time advanced pattern of A/H3N2 antigenic evolution seen globally during the A/H1N1 pandemic might be linked to modest NPIs and enhanced natural selection from competition with high circulation of A/H1N1pdm09 worldwide."

d. Line 266 – Line 270: "Conversely, the lagged pattern of A/H3N2 evolution seen in Southeastern Asia during the COVID-19 pandemic could be attributed to limited influenza circulation and evolution due to human behaviour changes driven by stringent and long-lasting NPIs."

e. Line 303: The fact that during the 2021/2022 season, persistent lineages in East Asia rarely mixed with those from the other two sub-regions, while mixing was at typical levels between Southeast Asia and South Asia (Fig. 5f) could be attributed to the uniquely stringent NPIs and international travel restrictions that were still in place in China over this period."

5. Line 158: It is out of place to refer to the number of 'Markov jump counts' here without providing more detail on the methods in-line. I suggest including more detail and 'translating' this for the average reader here and throughout. Further, in Fig.2, referring to the Markov jump counts on the y-axis, despite being specific, is uninformative of the result's ecological or public health impact. You mention in text 'viral movement' which is better so suggest changing these axis labels (and in the extended data figures) and transforming the axis to be meaningful e.g. as a relative proportion.

6. Line 200: Please clarify the meaning of "relatively consistently", which is redundant and ambiguous.

7. Line 230: Saying "a subtype whose antigenic map has been clearly resolved" comes across as definitive and is not an accurate justification to only investigate A/H3N2. I think conducting the same analyses for B/Victoria using genetic distances is warranted. This should be complemented by a sensitivity analysis of the A/H3N2 genetic distance over time and compared to the results of the antigenic distance. The results for B/Victoria can then be interpreted in the context of A/H3N2 antigenic distance vs A/H3N2 genetic distance results.

8. Line 327: "disappeared almost completely during both pandemic-related disruptions" followed by "with the exception of ..." is indirect and potentially misleading. Please be more specific e.g. both A/H3N2 and B/Victoria export dropped during COVID. However, during the 2009 pandemic

9. A large omission is an analysis of the impact of the border closure of mainland China, and, what happened after the borders were reopened. You say, "persistent lineages in East Asia rarely mixed with those from the other two sub-regions ... could be attributed to the uniquely stringent NPIs and international travel restrictions that were still in place in China over this period." This is another example of a testable hypothesis. The positive coefficient of overall airline traffic (for the entire study period?) is insufficient to make such a conclusion. We already know that airline traffic is a positive predictor of transmission. But this should be complemented by factors such as the reduction in airline traffic during the pandemic period, where the effect is compared to the "expected" result during the interpandemic period. Given the model is asymmetric, airline traffic should also be expanded to include departures and arrivals, and their effect on transitions from and to China and other regions.

10. What about the difference in NPIs and measures employed within SEA? A single measure of "Airline traffic" again is too vague. An interesting question is the antigenic/genetic evolution within SEA regions that employed different internal NPIs vs external i.e. border controls. Differences in NPIs within the regions could have a large impact on the diversity of strains within each region, which, depending on border measures, could affect the rate at which highly divergent are then exported into naïve regions.

11. Concluding "More population-based and modelling studies are required to deepen the understanding of the exact mechanisms underpinning our observations." is the kind of results I would like to see added here. I don't expect much advanced modelling, but the addition of more factors in existing models and new statistical tests are necessary to support many of the claims made throughout.

12. Data and Code availability are insufficient. Currently, only the XMLs are provided to replicate the runs in BEAST. Other analyses of the data and results and replication of the figures are not possible right now.

(Remarks on code availability)

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Reviewer #2

(Remarks to the Author)

Here the authors examine the global patterns of influenza virus A and B movement using genomic, epidemiological and air travel between the 2009 H1N1 pandemic and the 2020 CoVID pandemic. The paper shows that major global perturbations in human mobility and behavior can impact the genetic and phenotypic evolution globally distributed diseases. The paper is well written. The use of the epochal model to allow for the spatial transition during inter-pandemic and pandemic time-periods is an elegant approach. My comments are minor.

Comments

What is the trunk proportions/trunk location states of the other subsampling strategies? Which subsampling strategy is shown in Figure 3? Was the analysis of all subsampling strategies consistent?

Was there any evidence that the sampling strategies impacted the posterior probabilities of the discrete states? Did you assess the impact of sampling bias (tip-swap randomization in Edwards et al 2011)

Why did you choose the Constant coalescent prior and strict clock? Did you assess the model and tree prior? These decisions will impact the tree and the subsequent DTA. Why did you choose a SkyGrid with 2 change points for the SouthEastern analyses - again with a constant clock, did you assess the appropriate clock model?

The authors state a couple of times that "A/H3N2, a subtype whose antigenic map has been clearly resolved" First point - the reference cited (Ref 27) does not support this statement. Further, I don't know what is meant by this statement. Is this the HI derived antigenic map? Is this the mapped sequence-based calculation of antigenic distance? If referring to the HI-derived antigenic map, I contend that this statement is factually incorrect. The utility of HI data in generating an antigenic map of HI data, especially in the time period analyzed, has been called into question. There is evidence that this assay may be fundamentally flawed. Regardless - I am confused by the statement and not sure what it refers to.

Line 266: Speculation - move to discussion

"Conversely, the lagged pattern of A/H3N2 evolution seen in Southeastern Asia during the COVID-19 pandemic could be attributed to limited influenza circulation and evolution due to human behaviour changes driven by stringent and long-lasting NPIs."

Line 280: What are these numbers referring to? "52.6% (1- 85.0/179.4)"

Line 305: This statement is a bit strong and may be an over interpretation of the results

"The fact that during the 2021/2022 season persistent lineages in East Asia rarely mixed with those from the other two sub-regions, while mixing was at typical levels between Southeast Asia and South Asia (Fig. 5f) could be attributed to the uniquely stringent NPIs and international travel restrictions that were still in place in China over this period."

JBahl

(Remarks on code availability)

Version 1:

Reviewer comments:

Reviewer #1

(Remarks to the Author)

Based on the revisions made to the manuscript, I'm happy to say the authors have addressed many of the concerns raised in the initial review. I particularly appreciate the consideration taken to add more detailed comparison between the H1N1pdm09 and SARS-CoV-2 pandemics. The expanded analysis better highlights the distinct impacts of the two pandemics with statistical support, which strengthen the overall study's claims. I have only one comment:

1. Line 207-209: The end of the sentence here makes this somewhat difficult to read "after epidemic alignment at median week for the timing of each season". Please modify as possible. I suggest starting with the method to something like: "After aligning the peaks of each season to their median epidemic week, we subsequently averaged the number of viral movement events from Southeast Asia to temperate regions during the interpandemic period."

(Remarks on code availability)

Reviewer #2

(Remarks to the Author)

The authors have made a thorough and good faith effort to address all of my concerns. I have no further concerns at this time.

JBahl

(Remarks on code availability)

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Response to referees' comment: "Disruption of seasonal influenza circulation and evolution during the 2009 H1N1 and COVID-19 pandemics in Southeastern Asia"

We thank the reviewers for their comments on our manuscript. Below we list the major changes made followed by a point-by-point response.

1. We've performed additional quantitative analysis to more thoroughly compare the two pandemics.
2. We've provided evidence to show that airline traffic data are a good proxy of the strength of behavioural changes and non-pharmaceutical interventions during the COVID-19 pandemic. We refer to this proxy measure as the air travel-related stringency index throughout both pandemics.
3. We've incorporated additional potential correlates of transmission and spread of influenza into a statistical model (random forest) to evaluate their relative importance in determining influenza activity during the two pandemics.
4. We've performed additional analyses as per suggestions from reviewers:
 - We added analyses of evolutionary patterns for the B/Victoria lineage using genetic distance (instead of antigenic distance) and also compared the consistency of using antigenic distance versus genetic distance for A/H3N2.
 - We incorporated the temporal variation in overall airline traffic as a predictor of overall migration rates (in addition to using pairwise air traffic matrix as a predictor of relative migration rates). This resulted in slightly different estimates for key parameters. However, the main findings and conclusions of our paper remain unchanged.
 - We added analyses of viral movement within China and from/to China during and after the border closures.
 - We added sensitivity analyses to test the robustness of inferred trunk locations among different subsampling strategies.
5. We've removed the speculative statements from the Results section and added more text in the Discussion to highlight the ecological and public health implications of the results.
6. We've added the code and data to reproduce the main results into a public repository for review.

Review round: 1

Reviewer #1:

Summary & Recommendation

This study offers insights into the spread of seasonal influenza A/H3N2 and B/Victoria globally and within Southeast Asia, a region known as a significant source of global influenza transmission. The author's examination of how the H1N1pdm09 and SARS-CoV-2 pandemics disrupted influenza transmission is a particularly relevant question. However, the study needs to improve in this regard.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their time and constructive comments to improve this work.

Firstly, the comparison between the two pandemics is underdeveloped. Given each pandemic's distinct nature and impact, a more thorough comparison is warranted. The results tend to be overly descriptive, particularly in discussing travel disruptions, rather than delving into a deeper, more analytical comparison of the pandemics' effects on spread. For example, there are many instances where changes in air traffic are said to likely explain the differences. Though this is most certainly true, it is relatively shallow. Many of the claims could be tested, and more effort should be devoted to investigating the effect of the two pandemics in a statistically robust way besides simple descriptives.

Response: We agree with the reviewer that a more thorough comparison between two pandemics and more statistical analyses are warranted to strengthen our work.

We first collected data and covariates beyond the airline traffic data that reflect the distinct nature and impact of the two pandemics, with details provided in **Supplementary Table 1** and **Supplementary Figs. 3-5**. In particular **Supplementary Table 1** and **Supplementary Fig. 3** provide side-by-side comparisons of interventions and epidemiological impacts for the pandemics. We also estimate an air traffic-related stringency index, as described in response to a later comment (**pages 10-11**).

Besides the factors listed above, other factors, such as population immunity and detailed NPI implementation beyond air travel control (e.g., mask wearing, avoidance of indoor and crowded spaces, hand washing) could also impact influenza circulation. Unfortunately, reliable and complete information about these factors either does not exist or is not available publicly. This is especially true for the 2009 H1N1 pandemic and the large geographical region we're studying.

We've added the above comparison in the main text (see below). We've also performed statistical analyses using the above covariates in response to a later specific comment (pages 7-8).

“The two pandemics occurred under heterogeneous conditions (Supplementary Table 1, Supplementary Figs. 3-5). Since there are few records of the stringency of travel measures and NPIs during the H1N1 pandemic, we calculated an air travel-related stringency index (other behavioural changes are not included), based on the strong correlation between airline traffic and the COVID-19 stringency index during the COVID-19 pandemic (Supplementary Table 2). In comparison to the 2009 H1N1 pandemic, the COVID-19 pandemic was associated with a far higher air travel-related stringency index (Supplementary Fig. 3). To further determine correlates with seasonal influenza activity during the pandemic seasons, we built a random forest model to assess the importance of predictors. We identified the COVID-19 stringency index as the most important predictor associated with the decline of seasonal influenza activity during the COVID-19 pandemic, while the socio-demographic index (a composite indicator constructed from income per capita, average years of schooling, and total fertility rate¹) played the most important role during the 2009 A/H1N1 pandemic (Supplementary Fig. 6)”

Supplementary Fig. 3 | Case incidence and stringency index in Southeastern Asia during the two pandemics. a) Reported cases per million people in Southeastern Asia during the 2009 H1N1 (blue) and COVID-19 (red) pandemics. Data of H1N1pdm09 cases in several sublocations (Bhutan, Brunei, Macao (China), Myanmar, Nepal, Taiwan (China), East Timor) are not

available. **b)** Compound airline traffic indicator during the 2009 H1N1 (solid blue line) and COVID-19 pandemics (solid red line) in Southeastern Asia. Pattern consistency of compound airline traffic indicator (solid red line) with the COVID-19 Stringency Index (dashed line) during the COVID-19 pandemic is also shown. The COVID-19 Stringency Index in Southeastern Asia is a population-weighted average among countries.

Supplementary Table 1. Characteristics of two pandemics.

	2009 H1N1 pandemic	COVID-19 pandemic	Sources
Case incidence in Southeastern Asia (cases per million people)	Low [#] (Supplementary Fig. 3a)	High (Supplementary Fig. 3a)	2-4
Viral transmissibility (R ₀)	1.7	2.5	5
Cross immunity with seasonal influenza virus	High/moderate	Low	6,7
Air travel-related stringency index in Southeastern Asia	Low* (Supplementary Fig. 3b)	High (Supplementary Fig. 3b)	OAG and ⁸
Socio-demographic index (SDI) in Southeastern Asia	Low (Supplementary Fig. 4)	High (Supplementary Fig. 4)	9
Humidity	Periodic fluctuation (Supplementary Fig. 5)		European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)
Temperature	Periodic fluctuation (Supplementary Fig. 5)		

[#] The under-ascertainment of the true number of infected individuals during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic is assumed to be more severe than the COVID-19 pandemic due to the limited monitoring capacity.

* Air travel-related stringency indexes during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic in Southeastern Asia use the compound airline traffic indicator as a proxy.

Given this, many of the results echo findings from previous studies, which diminishes the originality of the work. Without additional investigation, many of the observations made and associated claims are presented circumstantially, with the remaining results mostly repeating previous work, which the authors indirectly acknowledge by frequently citing and noting the consistency of their findings with prior work.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their critical insight but note that, to the best of our knowledge, our study represents the first attempt to compare the impact of both pandemic events on seasonal influenza circulation across a large geographic region using phylodynamic approaches. Most empirical work to date has focused on the impacts of an individual pandemic

on seasonal influenza circulation in a single country (see for example Xie et al. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ve/veac062>). Our work also explores the internal dispersal network in Southeastern Asia, which to the best of our knowledge has not been fully addressed yet (see examples here: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1109314108> & www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.1154137, which specifically mentions that “*the structure of the circulation network within East-Southeast Asia is unknown*”).

Compared to our own prior work (<https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.12.20.23300299>, accepted for publication in September 2024), the present work considers a different temporal (one versus two pandemics) and spatial resolution (region versus sublocation/country level). We also focused on different research questions, such as the identification of persistent lineages, antigenic evolution patterns, internal dispersal at the country level, as well as newly added analyses in this revision. Nevertheless, we do acknowledge that our work in part overlaps with and updates prior work and hence we discuss our work in context of these prior studies. Our work remains significant and generalises previous results by considering a finer-resolution geographic region across an unprecedented 18 influenza seasons with a larger genetic dataset.

The study would, therefore, benefit from a more robust statistical analysis quantifying the specific impacts of each pandemic on A/H3N2 and B/Victoria transmission. This would provide a better understanding of how these global events influenced seasonal influenza dynamics. I also felt there needed to be more about the ecological and public health implications of the results, with many important results presented without much interpretation.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their suggestion. We’ve added more statistical analyses in detail in response to later specific comments (**pages 7-8**). We also have added text to the Discussion to highlight the ecological and public health implications.

“These findings have several public health implications. First, seasonal influenza epidemics occur each year while pandemics only occur sporadically, thus interactions between seasonal respiratory pathogens and pandemics are also likely to occur in the future. Understanding the circulation patterns during these two pandemics may enhance preparedness against influenza outbreaks in inter-pandemic seasons and when facing future public health emergencies. Future work should model the impact of different types of interventions on the dynamics of seasonal influenza both in Southeastern Asia and globally to guide mitigation strategies. Second, temporally varying trunk locations within Southeastern Asia support the need for geographically extensive virological and genomic surveillance in this region, allowing for earlier identification of antigenically novel strains and thereby providing a longer lead time for developing and rolling out effective vaccines. A strong collaboration between WHO South-East Asia and WHO Western Pacific regions remains vital to maintain a high surveillance intensity across Southeastern Asia that in turn enhances pandemic preparedness. Third, the complex internal

dispersal network highlights the importance of country-specific vaccination strategies against seasonal influenza (e.g., vaccine strain and vaccine timing) ¹⁰, in particular in the context of altered seasonality and interrupted vaccination rollout during and after the pandemic. Establishing a global influenza migration network at a finer geographic scale (e.g., country level; over 120 WHO Member States have contributed to influenza surveillance as of May 2024 ²) also holds promise for optimising vaccine recommendations tailored to each country's future influenza outbreaks. Fourth, a new pandemic may reshape the landscape of influenza invasion and co-circulation based on ecological coexistence theory ¹¹. Further, changes in human-animal contact, the human-environment interface, and climate conditions could influence the viral evolution and emergence of novel influenza strains. Integrating ecological and social processes into activities of surveillance networks helps us better understand the drivers of influenza circulation and evolution.”

As such, I recommend major revisions, including additional work, with more specific comments below.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their comments and have addressed the specific comments below.

Comments

1. The title should be more specific. which is specific to A/H3N2 and B/Victoria during the H1N1pdm09 and SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. e.g. Disruption of seasonal A/H3N2 and B/Victoria circulation ...”. While it would be obvious why these two were chosen, it is better to be specific here and throughout, such as the subheadings.

Response: Thank you for the suggestion. While we agree with the reviewer that it's better to be specific, we don't consider it necessary in this case and believe adding subtype/lineages to the main title makes the title less accessible to a general audience (while pushing the title length too far above the 15 word limit). As the reviewer states, it is obvious why these two subtype/lineages were chosen. In fact, A/H3N2 and B/Victoria are the only seasonal influenza subtype/lineages that circulated before the 2009 A/H1N1 pandemic and continue to circulate today. However, we've now added the two specific pandemics to the title “*Disruption of seasonal influenza circulation and evolution during the 2009 H1N1 and COVID-19 pandemics in Southeastern Asia*”. We changed the subheadings using specific subtype/lineages accordingly throughout the manuscript.

2. Line 130. I think “Potential elimination” is a better term than disappearance.

Response: We agreed and changed it throughout the manuscript.

3. Line 149: “First quarter of 2010” Please be specific about months(s) to avoid confusion.

Response: Thanks, we have added the information and now specify that the first quarter is from January to March.

4. Line 151 to 153: There are a number of claims throughout the paper, here included, that could be easily tested. Many results are presented descriptively alongside each other and hypothesised as causative but not tested. For example, it should be simple enough to show the association between air traffic and the intensity of circulation controlling for seasonality. I’ve listed some additional areas where similar conclusions or loosely descriptive hypotheses are presented, which should be addressed with new work:

a. Line 187: “likely resulting in sustained exports from Southeastern Asia”

b. Line 209: “possibly due to the reduction of human mobility and subsequent lineage movement”

c. Line 264 “The time advanced pattern of A/H3N2 antigenic evolution seen globally during the A/H1N1 pandemic might be linked to modest NPIs and enhanced natural selection from competition with high circulation of A/H1N1pdm09 worldwide.”

d. Line 266 – Line 270: “Conversely, the lagged pattern of A/H3N2 evolution seen in Southeastern Asia during the COVID-19 pandemic could be attributed to limited influenza circulation and evolution due to human behaviour changes driven by stringent and long-lasting NPIs.”

e. Line 303: The fact that during the 2021/2022 season, persistent lineages in East Asia rarely mixed with those from the other two sub-regions, while mixing was at typical levels between Southeast Asia and South Asia (Fig. 5f) could be attributed to the uniquely stringent NPIs and international travel restrictions that were still in place in China over this period.”

Response: We agree with the reviewer to avoid the speculative statements in the Results section and add statistical analyses.

Specifically, we’ve added statistical analyses for some of the speculative statements (Line 151 to 153, previous line number), revised/removed some of the statements that could not be formally tested (Line 187, Line 209, Line 303), and moved some remaining speculative statements (Line 264, Line 266 – Line 270) into the Discussion section. For example:

“In Southeastern Asia, the decline of B/Victoria positivity in 2020 was strongly associated with the reduction of among-country airline traffic flow (Pearson correlation coefficient: 0.89), after controlling for seasonality (calculating the changes relative to the baseline month before the pandemic).”

Furthermore, to provide additional statistical evaluation, we built a random forest model to determine relevant factors potentially associated with reductions in influenza activity, specifically among demographical, meteorologic, stringency index, and pandemic-related case incidence during the two pandemic events, respectively (**Supplementary Fig. 6**). Detailed descriptions of the methods have been provided in the main text and Methods. In **Supplementary Fig. 6**, in brief, we identified that the COVID-19 stringency index was the most important variable associated with the decline of influenza activity during the COVID-19 pandemic (**Supplementary Fig. 6b**), while the socio-demographic index (a composite indicator constructed from income per capita, average years of schooling, and total fertility rate, developed by the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation) played the most important role during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic (**Supplementary Fig. 6a**).

5. Line 158: It is out of place to refer to the number of ‘Markov jump counts’ here without providing more detail on the methods in-line. I suggest including more detail and ‘translating’ this for the average reader here and throughout. Further, in Fig.2, referring to the Markov jump counts on the y-axis, despite being specific, is uninformative of the result's ecological or public health impact. You mention in text ‘viral movement’ which is better so suggest changing these axis labels (and in the extended data figures) and transforming the axis to be meaningful e.g. as a relative proportion.

Response: We’ve replaced “Markov jump counts” with “viral movements” throughout the manuscript. We also adjusted the y-axis in **Fig. 2** and in other figures as per the suggestion.

6. Line 200: Please clarify the meaning of “relatively consistently”, which is redundant and ambiguous.

Response: We’ve removed the word “relatively”.

7. Line 230: Saying “a subtype whose antigenic map has been clearly resolved” comes across as definitive and is not an accurate justification to only investigate A/H3N2. I think conducting the same analyses for B/Victoria using genetic distances is warranted. This should be complemented by a sensitivity analysis of the A/H3N2 genetic distance over time and compared to the results of the antigenic distance. The results for B/Victoria can then be interpreted in the context of A/H3N2 antigenic distance vs A/H3N2 genetic distance results.

Response: As suggested, we analysed influenza B/Victoria, despite lack of a resolved antigenic map. First, we compared the consistency of A/H3N2 antigenic distance versus A/H3N2 genetic distance (**Fig 4** versus **Supplementary Fig. 11a-b**), showing that they are consistent with our main findings, except for the pattern during the COVID-19 pandemic (it's still more lagged compared to during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic, but more advanced than during the interpandemic period). We also performed the analyses for B/Victoria lineages using genetic distance (**Supplementary Fig. 11c-d**), and we added the results to the main text:

“Compared to A/H3N2, in Southeastern Asia, the time-advanced pattern of B/Victoria during the interpandemic period is absent, while the advanced pattern (by 8.5 months) during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic is still observed, and the lagged pattern (by 4.5 months) during the COVID-19 pandemic is only observed for persistent lineages (Supplementary Fig. 11c-d).”

8. Line 327: “disappeared almost completely during both pandemic-related disruptions” followed by “with the exception of ... “ is indirect and potentially misleading. Please be more specific e.g. both A/H3N2 and B/Victoria export dropped during COVID. However, during the 2009 pandemic

Response: We apologise for the potentially misleading statement, and have rephrased the sentence to avoid confusion:

“We demonstrated that typical autumn-winter waves of A/H3N2 and B/Victoria movements from Southeastern Asia to temperate regions disappeared almost completely during COVID-19 pandemic-related disruptions. However, B/Victoria lineage movement into temperate regions still occurred during the A/H1N1 pandemic.”

9. A large omission is an analysis of the impact of the border closure of mainland China, and, what happened after the borders were reopened. You say, “persistent lineages in East Asia rarely mixed with those from the other two sub-regions ... could be attributed to the uniquely stringent NPIs and international travel restrictions that were still in place in China over this period.” This is another example of a testable hypothesis. The positive coefficient of overall airline traffic (for the entire study period?) is insufficient to make such a conclusion. We already know that airline traffic is a positive predictor of transmission. But this should be complemented by factors such as the reduction in airline traffic during the pandemic period, where the effect is compared to the “expected” result during the interpandemic period. Given the model is asymmetric, airline traffic should also be expanded to include departures and arrivals, and their effect on transitions from and to China and other regions.

Response: We thank the reviewer for suggesting these specific analyses.

To expand on our analyses, we first summarised the information about border closures in China (**Supplementary Fig 14a**) and used our updated phylogeographic results to further analyse the viral movement within China and from/to China during and after the border closure (**Supplementary Fig 14b-c**). We found that overall airline traffic into and out of China correlated well with viral movement fluxes into and out of China (Pearson correlation coefficient: 0.91 and 0.93, respectively). The internal viral movement intensity in China recovered earlier and to a larger extent than cross-border movement from/to China, after border control measures were gradually relaxed.

The above analyses further support that during the 2021/2022 season (July 2021 to June 2022), limited viral movement occurred between China and other sub-locations in Southeastern Asia. This is consistent with low lineage mixing during that time period. We have also stated this more cautiously in the Results section.

In the previous version, the coefficient refers to the effect size of the air traffic matrix on the relative migration rate among locations for the entire time period. We further changed the time-inhomogeneous phylogeographic model to incorporate the airline traffic data in each epoch as a predictor of overall migration rate, so as to assess the role of temporal changes in the overall airline traffic in addition to their relative intensities (**Supplementary Table 4**). The finding that overall air traffic volumes act as the predictor of overall migration rate supports the role of reduction in airline traffic during the pandemic period as well.

As we included the epoch-specific asymmetric air traffic network in the generalised linear model as one of the covariates, the information of departures and arrivals would be considered when correlating it with the migration rates among sublocations (including inflow and outflows as well). In addition, we also noticed that the departure and arrival volumes of each sub-location are highly consistent over time (see an example: **Supplementary Fig 14a**).

10. What about the difference in NPIs and measures employed within SEA? A single measure of “Airline traffic” again is too vague. An interesting question is the antigenic/genetic evolution within SEA regions that employed different internal NPIs vs external i.e. border controls. Differences in NPIs within the regions could have a large impact on the diversity of strains within each region, which, depending on border measures, could affect the rate at which highly divergent are then exported into naïve regions.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their comment on the differences in NPIs and measures.

First, we would like to caution that while the NPIs and public health measures during the COVID-19 pandemic are easily accessible due to global, regional, and national effort for building a global repository and platform (see for an example: COVID-19 Stringency Index,

<https://ourworldindata.org/covid-stringency-index>), there seems to be no such indicator of NPI intensity (e.g., stringency index) reported during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic.

Alternatively, bearing in mind limitations to extrapolation, we can adopt airline traffic as a proxy of air travel-related stringency index during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic if we can establish a linear relationship between stringency index and airline traffic during the COVID-19 pandemic. We adopted the following method to build that:

Methods: To obtain a proxy stringency index for the H1N1 pandemic, we first examined the relationship between the COVID-19 stringency index and airline traffic during the COVID-19 pandemic for each sublocation in Southeastern Asia (**Supplementary Table 2**). Given the COVID-19 stringency index is a composite measure of nine response metrics, including internal movements, international travel controls, and other human behavioural changes⁸, we could only construct an air travel-related stringency index (compound airline traffic indicator) by considering both the within-sublocation airline traffic and international airline traffic from/to each sublocation. This indicator didn't cover other types of behaviours and policies beyond air travel, which should reflect part of the extent of NPIs. Note that since there is no internal airline traffic in Hong Kong (China), Macao (China) and Singapore, we constructed an indicator with only air travel from/to the sublocation for these three sublocations. In each sublocation, for each airline traffic indicator (domestic or international), we compared the change relative to the same month in 2019 (referred to as the baseline month). The baseline month represents a normal value for that month before the COVID-19 pandemic. Monthly baselines were used because of seasonal fluctuations in airline traffic. The composite indicator using airline traffic is then given by

$$100 - (Relative\ value\ domestic + Relative\ value\ international) \times 50$$

and serves as a proxy air travel-related stringency index. The indexes that are below zero are set to zero.

Because of the strong correlation between the compound airline traffic indicator and the COVID-19 stringency index (**Supplementary Table 2, Supplementary Figure 3**), we use the compound airline traffic indicator to also define an air travel-related stringency index for the H1N1 pandemic, using airline traffic in 2008 as a baseline. The associated results are presented in **Supplementary Fig. 3b**.

We fully agree with the importance of dissecting what factors drive virus evolution and diversity during the pandemics. However, we realised it's a complicated research question that should take into account not only internal and external NPIs, but also the population immunity level (see an example: Zhang et al., 10.1073/pnas.2312198120), viral interference among influenza subtypes (see an example: Perofsky et al., <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.91849.1>), as well as other

potential factors. Therefore, we acknowledge this as one of limitations and highlighted the importance of mechanistic modelling to dissect the whole process in the Discussion section:

“For example, the impact of domestic and international public health measures on viral evolution and diversity should merit more mechanistic investigation.”

11. Concluding “More population-based and modelling studies are required to deepen the understanding of the exact mechanisms underpinning our observations.” is the kind of results I would like to see added here. I don’t expect much advanced modelling, but the addition of more factors in existing models and new statistical tests are necessary to support many of the claims made throughout.

Response: We thank the reviewer for the comments on our statistical analyses which we have addressed in the responses above.

12. Data and Code availability are insufficient. Currently, only the XMLs are provided to replicate the runs in BEAST. Other analyses of the data and results and replication of the figures are not possible right now.

Response: We apologise for not making the analyses files available earlier. We have now made all data and code publicly available at https://github.com/zycfd/sea_flu.

Reviewer #1 (Remarks on code availability):

Data and Code availability are insufficient.

Currently, only the XMLs are provided to replicate the runs in BEAST.

Other analyses of the data and results and replication of the figures are not possible right now.

Response: All data and code are now available at https://github.com/zycfd/sea_flu. In addition, we include scripts for reproducing the figures in the manuscript.

Reviewer #2:

Here the authors examine the global patterns of influenza virus A and B movement using genomic, epidemiological and air travel between the 2009 H1N1 pandemic and the 2020 CoVID pandemic. The paper shows that major global perturbations in human mobility and behavior can impact the genetic and phenotypic evolution globally distributed diseases. The paper is well

written. The use of the epochal model to allow for the spatial transition during inter-pandemic and pandemic time-periods is an elegant approach. My comments are minor.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their positive assessment of our work.

Comments

What is the trunk proportions/trunk location states of the other subsampling strategies? Which subsampling strategy is shown in Figure 3? Was the analysis of all subsampling strategies consistent?

Response: We apologise for the lack of clarity on this. All the main analyses are performed under the even subsampling scheme, including those presented in **Figure 3**, and we have now added the details in each figure caption. We also present the additional results of the sensitivity analyses using other subsampling strategies, which clearly show that our main findings are largely robust to sub-sampling biases (**Supplementary Figs. 9-10**).

Was there any evidence that the sampling strategies impacted the posterior probabilities of the discrete states? Did you assess the impact of sampling bias (tip-swap randomization in Edwards et al 2011)

Response: We thank the reviewer for their comment on sampling biases and the posterior probabilities of phylogeographic analysis. Both are commonly acknowledged as issues in such studies.

In addition to differences in sub-sampling, many studies may suffer from biases due to unsampled locations (i.e., no data) and heterogeneous distribution of genome sequences, which has been highlighted in our previous review paper (Chen et al. 2024 *Lancet Microbe* [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247\(23\)00296-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247(23)00296-3)). To reduce potential biases resulting from the unavailability of pathogen genomes, we excluded several countries (North Korea, Mongolia, Pakistan, etc.) with limited public access to genomic data, and aggregated some genomic data to locations with lower resolution (Malaysia-Brunei, Indonesia-East Timor).

To address the first issue regarding the differences in posterior probabilities, we adopted multiple sub-sampling schemes to test the robustness of our inference. Using multiple sub-sampling schemes has been shown to expose and reduce the potential impact of sub-sampling biases in phylodynamic-related studies (see an overview here: Layan et al. 2023 *Virus Evolution*: <https://academic.oup.com/ve/article-abstract/9/1/vead010/7028398>). Layan et al. recommend the use of even sampling to address potential issues with sub-sampling (section “*Practical implications for the analysis of empirical datasets*”) which we followed. Other work on the large-scale circulation of influenza also adopted the even sub-sampling scheme (Bedford et al.

2015 Nature <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature14460>). We've added our rationale for using the even subsampling scheme in the main text and refer to the paper by Layan et al.

We also considered the potential for biases arising from the sub-sampling scheme that was recommended. Specifically, we adopted other sub-sampling schemes to test the robustness of our primary approach including influenza activity and population size in each sub-location as a proxy to inform the sampling process. We cannot directly compare the posterior probabilities of the discrete states of individual internal nodes between sampling strategies (because the sequence IDs that we used for the phylogeographic analyses are not the same among different sampling strategies), but we can compare the spatiotemporal patterns in a broad sense. For example, the movement from Southeastern Asia to temperate regions is robust to changes in the sampling strategy (**Supplementary Fig. 8**). Furthermore, we observe a similar pattern for the trunk location among different sampling strategies (**Supplementary Fig. 9**).

We've highlighted more on this point in the Discussion section:

*“First, inherent biases exist due to the nature of genetic data from heterogeneous genomic surveillance efforts and data sharing initiatives worldwide. To address these issues, we carefully downsampled genetic data geographically and temporally; our main conclusions are robust across various sets of genetic data from different sub-sampling schemes (**Supplementary Figs. 8-10 & 16**)”*

Why did you choose the Constant coalescent prior and strict clock? Did you assess the model and tree prior? These decisions will impact the tree and the subsequent DTA. Why did you choose a SkyGrid with 2 change points for the SouthEastern analyses - again with a constant clock, did you assess the appropriate clock model?

Response: Thanks for pointing this out. Generally, we set up the model based on the previous understanding of influenza virus population dynamics, relevant prior work, the amount of genomic data, and accessible computational resources/acceptable computational time. We detail our model choices below:

1. Our main analysis contains over 4,000 genetic sequences. It is computationally challenging to infer phylogenies of this size in any Bayesian framework including BEAST. In order to make the inference computationally tractable while still fully accounting for phylogenetic uncertainty, we used a simple tree prior and clock model.
2. Specifically, when setting up the model for our main phylogenetic analysis, we used a constant coalescent tree prior instead of a more flexible model (e.g., skyline, skygrid). As our analysis spans across many influenza seasons the average effective population size is roughly constant, and so a constant coalescent prior is not expected to introduce

major biases to the ages of internal nodes. Using a nonparametric method to properly model the seasonal dynamic is likely to complicate convergence in our analysis. For similar reasons, a constant coalescent prior was also used in previously published studies of seasonal influenza viruses (e.g. Bedford et al. 2015 Nature <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature14460>). We chose a strict molecular clock based on the well-known and strong correlation between the root-to-tip genetic distance and the sampling date in influenza virus HA sequences (minimum Pearson correlation coefficient: 0.95) (**Supplementary Fig. 17**). We note that an uncorrelated relaxed clock would result in introducing ~8000 more parameters in the model. We've added our rationales for using the model settings in the main text.

3. When running the internal analyses within Southeastern Asia, we reduced the number of sequences to ~2,000 and were able to achieve convergence under a more parameter-rich model. Therefore, we've chosen a Skygrid model to capture the seasonal dynamic. Our Skygrid model has grid points spaced at 6 month intervals, resulting in a total of 33 change points, not 2 as stated by the reviewer.

We have added details on the above rationales to the Methods section.

“The simple constant coalescent prior was chosen to manage the computational burden. A strict molecular clock model was adopted due to the strong correlations between root-to-tip genetic distance and collection date (minimum Pearson correlation coefficient: 0.95) (Supplementary Fig. 17).”

The authors state a couple of times that "A/H3N2, a subtype whose antigenic map has been clearly resolved" First point - the reference cited (Ref 27) does not support this statement. Further, I don't know what is meant by this statement. Is this the HI derived antigenic map? Is this the mapped sequence-based calculation of antigenic distance? If referring to the HI-derived antigenic map, I contend that this statement is factually incorrect. The utility of HI data in generating an antigenic map of HI data, especially in the time period analyzed, has been called into question. There is evidence that this assay may be fundamentally flawed. Regardless - I am confused by the statement and not sure what it refers to.

Response: We apologise for not clarifying that we used a sequence-based calculation of antigenic distance and not an HI-derived antigenic map.

For the first point, the reference (previously Ref 27) did have related statements in the Methods section (*“Because antigenic site maps for influenza B have not yet been established, ...”*) and presented the H3 antigenic site map in their Appendix. However, it's not the original reference and we've provided additional references to support this argument.

We've also clarified this statement to add more details and ensure that the text is clear on the use of a sequence-based calculation of antigenic distance rather than HI-derived data.

In response to the first Reviewer, we've also added an analysis of evolutionary patterns for B/Victoria lineage using genetic distance, in the context of the consistency of antigenic distance versus genetic distance for A/H3N2 (**Supplementary Fig. 11**).

Line 266: Speculation - move to discussion

"Conversely, the lagged pattern of A/H3N2 evolution seen in Southeastern Asia during the COVID-19 pandemic could be attributed to limited influenza circulation and evolution due to human behaviour changes driven by stringent and long-lasting NPIs."

Response: Thanks for this suggestion. We've moved it to Discussion.

Line 280: What are these numbers referring to? "52.6% (1- 85.0/179.4)"

Response: 85.0 refers to the number of viral movement events per year during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic, and 179.4 refers to average of that during the interpandemic period. Therefore, this percentage (52.6%) denotes the reduced proportion. We've removed the contents in parentheses to avoid confusion.

Line 305: This statement is a bit strong and may be an over interpretation of the results

"The fact that during the 2021/2022 season persistent lineages in East Asia rarely mixed with those from the other two sub-regions, while mixing was at typical levels between Southeast Asia and South Asia (Fig. 5f) could be attributed to the uniquely stringent NPIs and international travel restrictions that were still in place in China over this period."

Response: We've softened this language and provided additional supportive analyses (**Supplementary Fig 14**, also in response to a comment by the first reviewer).

References

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- 2 World Health Organization. *Global Influenza Surveillance and Response System (GISRS)*, <<https://www.who.int/initiatives/global-influenza-surveillance-and-response-system>> (2024).
- 3 World Health Organization. *WHO COVID-19 dashboard*, <<https://data.who.int/dashboards/covid19/deaths?n=c>> (2024).
- 4 Dong, E., Du, H. & Gardner, L. An interactive web-based dashboard to track COVID-19 in real time. *The Lancet. Infectious diseases* **20**, 533-534, doi:10.1016/s1473-3099(20)30120-1 (2020).
- 5 Petersen, E. *et al.* Comparing SARS-CoV-2 with SARS-CoV and influenza pandemics. *The Lancet. Infectious diseases* **20**, e238-e244, doi:10.1016/s1473-3099(20)30484-9 (2020).
- 6 Matera, L. *et al.* An overview on viral interference during SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. *Frontiers in pediatrics* **11**, 1308105, doi:10.3389/fped.2023.1308105 (2023).
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- 8 Hale, T. *et al.* A global panel database of pandemic policies (Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker). *Nature human behaviour* **5**, 529-538, doi:10.1038/s41562-021-01079-8 (2021).
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- 10 Saha, S. *et al.* Influenza seasonality and vaccination timing in tropical and subtropical areas of southern and south-eastern Asia. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* **92**, 318-330, doi:10.2471/blt.13.124412 (2014).
- 11 Park, S. W., Cobey, S., Metcalf, C. J. E., Levine, J. M. & Grenfell, B. T. Predicting pathogen mutual invasibility and co-circulation. *Science* **386**, 175-179, doi:10.1126/science.adq0072 (2024).

Review round: 2

Reviewer #1:

Based on the revisions made to the manuscript, I'm happy to say the authors have addressed many of the concerns raised in the initial review. I particularly appreciate the consideration taken to add more detailed comparison between the H1N1pdm09 and SARS-CoV-2 pandemics. The expanded analysis better highlights the distinct impacts of the two pandemics with statistical support, which strengthen the overall study's claims. I have only one comment:

Response: We thank the reviewer for their positive assessment of our work.

1. Line 207-209: The end of the sentence here makes this somewhat difficult to read "after epidemic alignment at median week for the timing of each season". Please modify as possible. I suggest starting with the method to something like: "After aligning the peaks of each season to their median epidemic week, we subsequently averaged the number of viral movement events from Southeast Asia to temperate regions during the interpandemic period."

Response: We have modified the sentence accordingly.

Reviewer #2:

The authors have made a thorough and good faith effort to address all of my concerns. I have no further concerns at this time.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their favorable assessment of our work.